

A Topological Construction to Solve Poincare's Conjecture

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Abstract. On this work its develops the requirements to construct a compact k-dimensional manifold A without boundary since the scalar field defined with $a = \frac{l}{l'} = \frac{p \sqrt[n]{\pi^m}}{q \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'}}$ and establish the main scope about the trivial fundamental group on Poincare's Conjecture for rational and irrational numbers.

Keyword: Poincare; Irrational; Manifold; Topological

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1 Introduction

The original phrasing was as follows:

Consider a compact 3-dimensional manifold V without boundary. Is it possible that the fundamental group of V could be trivial, even though V is not homeomorphic to the 3-dimensional sphere?

To define the 3-dimensional manifold V; lets start by establish next properties about open sets and topological manifold.

Lets name:

$$l = q \sqrt[n]{\pi^m} \in \mathfrak{R} \dots(1)$$

and

$$a = \frac{l}{l'} = \frac{p \sqrt[n]{\pi^m}}{q \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'}}} \dots(2)$$

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where $p, q, n, n', m, m' \in \mathfrak{R}$

Take into consideration that term given on (1) can be used to write some irrational numbers like the Gelfond- Schneider constant or Hilbert number when we match this expression such number; giving values to q, n and m.

i.e.

$$2^{\sqrt{2}} = q^{\sqrt[n]{\pi^m}}$$

Clearing pi-root we could have:

$$q = \frac{2^{\sqrt{2}}}{\sqrt[n]{\pi^m}}$$

Hence q could be defined using different values of n and m and therefore Hilbert number could have different ways to express its value.

Now define \mathbf{a} like the term of each coordinate on k-dimensions; therefore any point $a \in A$ on a k-dimensional space can be write as:

$$a \in R^k = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = \left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m'_1}}}, \frac{p_2 \sqrt[n_2]{\pi^{m_2}}}{q_2 \sqrt[n_2]{\pi^{m'_2}}}, \dots, \frac{p_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m'_k}}} \right)$$

With this on mind lets construct a 3-dimensional manifold; starting by establish next three conditions to construct first a topological manifold.

1. Locally Euclidean
2. Hausdorff
3. Verify Second Countable Axiom

[1] A is Locally Euclidean

Lets prove that every point $a \in A$ has a neighbourhood which is homeomorphic to real k-space \mathfrak{R}^k by establishing the next conditions for a function f between both topological spaces.

Remember that on Euclidean space \mathfrak{R}^k the Euclidean topology is the natural topology induced by the Euclidean metric. Also take into consideration that to be homeomorphic both spaces need to be of same dimension.

[1.1] f is one-to-one i.e.

Take $f(a_1), f(a_2) \in \mathfrak{R}^k$

Now take into consideration next properties about term given on (2)

·) For (2) we have with $m = m' = 0$ and $n, n' \in \mathfrak{R}$

$$a = \frac{p}{q} \in \mathfrak{R}$$

This should mean that any value that could have $f(a) \in R^k$ space can be described using early condition; including those cases when q is trivial.

·) To consider the possibility to establish more values associated with pi-roots on both topological spaces the term given for \mathbf{a} will be used complete explicitly.

If $f(a_1) = f(a_2)$ then

Using term given on (2) on both sides of early condition we have:

$$f(a_1) = f\left(\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right)_{a_1}, \dots, \left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)_{a_1}\right)$$

and

$$f(a_2) = f\left(\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right)_{a_2}, \dots, \left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)_{a_2}\right)$$

by "if condition" then

$$\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right)_{a_1} = \left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right)_{a_2}$$

.

.

$$\left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)_{a_2} = \left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)_{a_2}$$

therefore

$$(a_1) = (a_2)$$

Hence f is one-to-one

[1.2] f is onto

If

$$f(a) = f\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m'_1}}}, \dots, \frac{p_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right) \in \mathfrak{R}^k$$

$$f(a) = \left(f_1\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right), \dots, f_k\left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)\right) \in \mathfrak{R}^k$$

Applying inverse function f^{-1} we have:

$$a = \left(f_1^{-1}\left(f_1\left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m'_1}}}\right)\right), \dots, f_k^{-1}\left(f_k\left(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right)\right)\right) \in A$$

Simplifying

$$a = \left(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n_1]{\pi^{m'_1}}}, \dots, \frac{p_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n_k]{\pi^{m'_k}}}\right) \in A$$

Hence

$$\exists a \in A \forall f(a) \in \mathfrak{R}^k$$

Therefore

f is onto

Therefore f is a bijection

[1.3] f is continuous

Def.

A function

$$f : X \rightarrow Y$$

between two topological spaces X and Y is continuous if for every open set $V \subseteq Y$, the inverse image

$$f^{-1}(V) = \{x \in X | f(x) \in V\}$$

is an open subset of X .

Proof.

Lets call $V \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^k$ the image of f

Like before

$$f(a) = (f_1(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_1}}})_a, \dots, f_k(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_k}}})_a) \in V$$

Now consider $f(c), f(r) \in V$ such that

$$f(c) = (f_1(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_1}}})_c, \dots, f_k(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_k}}})_c) \in V$$

and

$$f(r) = (f_1(\frac{p_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_1}}}{q_1 \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_1}}})_r, \dots, f_k(\frac{p_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_k}}}{q_k \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_k}}})_r) \in V$$

Using Euclidean distance to calculate length of interval between points $\mathbf{f}(c)$ and $\mathbf{f}(r)$ we have:

$$d(f(c), f(r)) \in V \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^k = \sqrt{(f_1(\frac{p_r \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_r}}}{q_r \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_r}}})_r - f_1(\frac{p_c \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_c}}}{q_c \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_c}}})_c)^2 + \dots + (f_k(\frac{p_r \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_r}}}{q_r \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_r}}})_r - f_k(\frac{p_c \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m_c}}}{q_c \sqrt[n]{\pi^{m'_c}}})_c)^2 =}$$

with $f(r) \neq f(c)$ then $d(f(c), f(r)) > 0$

Note that equation for $d(f(c), f(r))$ establish the square root of the equation of a k-sphere of radius equal ϵ

Lets take a point $f(a)$ into k-sphere and establish next fact by Law of Cosines:

$$\sqrt{d(f(c), f(a))^2 + d(f(a), f(r))^2 - 2d(f(c), f(a)) \cdot d(f(a), f(r)) \cos < f(c)f(a)f(r) >} = d(f(c), f(r))$$

where $< f(c)f(a)f(r) >$ is the angle formed by the three points indicated early.

Hence

$$d(f(c), f(a)) < d(f(c), f(r))$$

Like

$$d(f(c), f(r)) = \epsilon$$

Therefore

$$f(a) \in V \text{ fulfilled condition } d(f(c), f(a)) < \epsilon$$

Hence $\exists \epsilon$ that satisfied next condition to establish an open set in V

$$B(f(c), f(r)) = \{f(a) \in V | d(f(c), f(a)) < \epsilon\}$$

sometimes named with etiquette $B_f(i)$

To fulfilled condition about V to be open now define next topological properties:

Let

$$f(a) \in B(f(c_i), f(r_i)) \text{ and } f(a) \in B(f(c_j), f(r_j))$$

with $i \neq j$

$$\text{then } f(a) \in B(f(c_i), f(r_i)) \cup B(f(c_j), f(r_j))$$

Like $B_f(i)$ is open and $B_f(j)$ is open therefore union set is open

Besides if $f(a) = f(c_k)$ and $f(r_k) \in V$

$$\exists \epsilon_k \text{ such that } d(f(c_k), f(a_k)) < \epsilon_k$$

Therefore

$$B(f(c_k), f(r_k)) = \{f(a_k) \in V \mid d(f(c_k), f(a_k)) < \epsilon_k\}$$

Let $f(a_k) \in B_f(k)$ and $f(a_k) \in B(f(c_l), f(r_l))$

Therefore

$$f(a_k) \in B_f(k) \cup B_f(l)$$

furthermore like $B_f(k)$ is open and $B_f(l)$ is open therefore union set is open.

Note this property maintains $\forall f(a) \in V$

Hence V is open by $\bigcup_{i \in I} B_f(i) \in V$

In the other hand note that same property also maintains for

$$\bigcap_{i \in I} B_f(i) \in V; \forall f(a) \in V$$

Hence V is open by $\bigcup_{i \in I} B_f(i) \in V$

Hence V is open.

Later if we take $f(a) \in V$ and apply inverse function, such that $f^{-1}(f(a)) \in f^{-1}(V)$ then we have for every $a \in A$ an associated open set in V by early procedure.

Note that as before by Cosine Law procedure made to establish an open set $B(f(c), f(r)) \in V$; also maintains for $a \in B(c, r) \in W \subseteq A$. W is also named like the pre-image of f .

Even more; procedure to establish that V is open also maintains for W . Hence this means that W is open by $\bigcap_{i \in I} B_{f(i)} \in V$ and $\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \in V$ therefore W is open.

Hence $\exists B_f(i) \in V; \forall a \in B_i \in W \subseteq A$

\therefore

$$f^{-1}(V) = \{a \in A | f(a) \in V\}$$

[1.4] f^{-1} is continuous

Procedure to prove that f is continuous is analogous for f^{-1}

Hence

$$f^{-1}(W) = \{f(a) \in V | a \in W\} \text{ is an open set of } A.$$

[2] A is Hausdorff

Def.

Points x and y in a topological space X can be separated by neighbourhoods if there exists a neighbourhood U of x and a neighbourhood V of y such that U and V are disjoint $U \cap V = \emptyset$. X is a Hausdorff space if any two distinct points in X are separated by neighbourhoods.

Lets consider two open sets U and V on \mathbf{A} such that disjoint property fulfill:

Diagram 1. Two open sets disjoint condition.

Def. Let $B_r(v)$ and $B_s(u) \subseteq X$ be two open balls; if $d(v, u) = r + s$; $d(u, v) > r + s$ then $B_r(v) \cap B_s(u) = \phi$; i.e. X is a Hausdorff space.

Lets consider the points showed on early diagram and define its distances:

$$d(C_1, E_{11}) = r_1$$

$$d(C_2, E_{22}) = r_2$$

Now taking two points $a_1 \in V \in A$ and $a_2 \in U \in A$

$$a_1 \in U = \{a_1 \in A | d(a_1, C_1) = \epsilon_{11} < r_1\}$$

and

$$a_2 \in V = \{a_2 \in A | d(a_2, C_2) = \epsilon_{22} < r_2\}$$

With $\epsilon_{xx} :=$ open set radius

Hence

$$\epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} < d(C_1, C_2)$$

Therefore

A is Hausdorff

[3] Verify Second Countable Axiom

Def. a topological space T is second-countable if there exists some countable collection $U = \{U_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ of open subsets of T such that any open subset of T can be written as a union of elements of some subfamily of U .

Proof. We have define early that the elements of the pre-image W are the open sets $a \in B(c, r) \in W \subseteq A$. To verify SCA is necessary to prove first that $B(c, r)$ can be a countable collection of opens in W .

Lets take $a, c \in \mathfrak{R}^k$ and define its distance expression as next:
 $d(a, c) = \epsilon < r$

Being last also the condition to define an open set on A .

The collection of all distances defined on the pre-image W must satisfy trichotomy law considering another pair $a', c' \in A$

On the other hand by homeomorphism between A and \mathfrak{R}^k we have specifically for onto property that:

$$\text{if } f(c, a) = f(c', a') \text{ hence } (c, a) = (c', a')$$

This imply that trichotomy only establish

$$d(a, c) < d(a', c') \text{ or } d(a', c') < d(a, c)$$

Because every distance that satisfy $d(a, c) = d(a', c')$ is established always between the same pairs of points taken on the pre-image W .

Under this condition the collection of all distances between pairs $a, c \in W$ can be indexed; i.e. $B(c, a)$ is a countable collection of open sets on A .

Lets name the i -esim countable open set on real line like:

$$B_i(c, a) = \{a \in A | d(c, a)_i = \epsilon_i < r_i\}$$

If

$$a \in B_i(c, a)$$

hence

$$d(c, a) < d(c, r)$$

Left term establish next open set:

$$B(c, a') = \{a' \in A | d(c, a') < r' = d(c, a)\}$$

renaming and considering trichotomy we will have:

$$B(c, a') = \{a' \in A \mid d(c, a')_{i-1} < r' = d(c, a)_i\}$$

i.e.

$\forall a' \in B(c, a')$ is established

$$d(c, a')_{i-1} < d(c, a)_i < d(c, r)$$

and so on ...

Therefore

$$B_1(c, a^*) \subset \dots \subset B(c, a')_{i-1} \subset B(c, a)_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^i B_i = B_i$$

i.e. any open subset of T can be written as a union of elements of some subfamily of U

[4 Differential Manifold]

[4.1 Cover for A]

To construct a differential manifold we have to define formally an atlas on the topological space A .

Def. An atlas for a topological space M is an indexed family $\{(U_\alpha, \varphi_\alpha) : \alpha \in I\}$ of charts on M which covers M (that is, $\bigcup_{\alpha \in I} U_\alpha = M$). If for some fixed n , the image of each chart is an open subset of n -dimensional Euclidean space, then M is said to be an n -dimensional manifold.

Proof.

A chart (B, f) on A consists of an open subset B of A , and a homeomorphism f from B to an open subset B_f of some Euclidean space R^n .

We have defined conditions to establish a chart with ”**Locally Euclidean property**”; then is only necessary to define that the indexed family of open sets W (pre-image) cover A .

Lets take $W = Im(f) \subset A$ and $a \in A$ but $a \notin W$.

Establishing a second homeomorphism f' for $a \notin W$ we will have that: $\exists W'$ the pre-image of a second homeomorphism.

Let index both pre-images as W_i as well as both homeomorphism f_i with $i = \{1,2\}$ and establish a third homeomorphism f_3 with $a \notin W_1$ and W_2 .

Like before we will obtain another pre-image W_3 . Lets do this procedure i times; such that:

$\exists a \notin W_i$ and $a \in A$ with such that an homeomorphism f_i will be defined.

Like this procedure exhaustively use every $a \in A$ with $a \notin W_i$ hence we can affirm that:

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^I W_i = A$$

Therefore the indexed family W_i is a cover for A

Besides (W_i, f_i) is an atlas for A

[4.2 Transition Map is Differentiable]

Def. Given any $\alpha, \beta \in \Lambda$ the application $\tau_{\alpha, \beta} = \varphi_{\beta} \circ \varphi_{\alpha}^{-1} : \varphi_{\alpha}(U_{\alpha} \cap U_{\beta}) \rightarrow \varphi_{\beta}(U_{\alpha} \cap U_{\beta})$, called "**Transition Map**" is differentiable of order r .

Def. A real valued function f on an n -dimensional differentiable manifold M is called differentiable at a point $p \in M$ if (U, ϕ) is a differentiable chart where U is an open set in M containing p and $\phi : U \rightarrow \mathbf{R}^n$ is the map defining the chart, then f is differentiable at p if and only if

$$f \circ \phi^{-1} : \phi(U) \subset \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$$

is differentiable at $\phi(p)$, that is $f \circ \phi^{-1}$ is a differentiable function from the open set $\phi(U)$, considered as a subset of \mathbf{R}^n to \mathbf{R} .

Def. A function of several real variables $f : R^m \rightarrow R^n$ is said to be differentiable at a point x_0 if there exists a linear map $J : R^m \rightarrow R^n$ such that:

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{\|f(x_0+h) - f(x_0) - J(h)\|_{R^n}}{\|h\|_{R^m}} = 0$$

with

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \nabla^T f_1 \\ \vdots \\ \nabla^T f_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix}$$

Proof. Let be (U_α, ϕ_α) ; (U_β, ϕ_β) ; (U_ϕ, ϕ) with $\phi_\alpha, \phi_\beta, \phi$ differentiable functions and consider next definition:

Def. Let $A \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^n$, $a \in A$ and $f : A \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}^n$ injective, differentiable in a and such that $f(a) \in f(A)$.

Then f^{-1} is differentiable in $f(a)$ if and only if f^{-1} is continuous on $f(a)$ and $Df(a)$ is reversible that is, $\det|J(f(a))| \neq 0$

In such case $Df^{-1}(a) = |Df(a)|^{-1}$.

applying last definition to ϕ_α^{-1} we can affirm that $(U_\alpha, \phi_\alpha^{-1})$ is a differentiable chart.

Now consider the composition function:

$$\phi_\beta \circ \phi_\alpha^{-1} \circ \phi = \tau_{\alpha,\beta} \circ \phi$$

Such that $\phi(U_\alpha \cap U_\beta) \subset \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$

Like ϕ_α is an homeomorphism by former facts about f homeomorphism; ϕ_α^{-1} is an homeomorphism.

Like $\phi_\alpha^{-1}, \phi_\beta, \phi$ are homeomorphism hence $\phi_\beta \circ \phi_\alpha^{-1} \circ \phi = \tau_{\alpha,\beta} \circ \phi$ is an homeomorphism.

A continuous function is not necessary differentiable; but a differentiable function is necessarily continuous.

Besides remember that the composition of differentiable functions is differentiable.

By homeomorphism property about composition function; we can not conclude that $\tau_{\alpha,\beta} \circ \phi$ is differentiable.

However like we are requesting that $\phi_\alpha, \phi_\beta, \phi$ being differentiable hence composition $\phi_\beta \circ \phi_\alpha^{-1} \circ \phi = \tau_{\alpha,\beta} \circ \phi$ is differentiable.

Therefore $\phi_\beta \circ \phi_\alpha^{-1} = \tau_{\alpha,\beta}$ is differentiable of order $r = n-1$.

This means that all the partial derivatives of a function exist in a neighborhood of a point x_0 and are continuous at the point x_0 , then the function is differentiable at that point x_0 .

Hence the linear map J is given by the Jacobian matrix, an $n \times m$ matrix in this case.

[4.3] M manifolds is compact

Def. A compact manifold is a manifold that is compact as a topological space.

Def. This form of compactness holds for closed and bounded subsets of Euclidean space and is known as the Heine–Borel theorem.

Def. "Heine Borel Theorem". For a subset S of Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^n , the following two statements are equivalent:

S is closed and bounded S is compact, that is, every open cover of S has a finite subcover.

Proof.

To fulfilled the condition to be compact is enough to prove that A is closed and bounded.

Def. A subset W of a topological space (A, τ) is called closed if its complement $A \setminus W$ is an open subset of (A, τ) ; that is, if $A \setminus W \in \tau$.

We have defined before that $\bigcup_{i=1}^I W_i$ cover A; where $W_i \in A$ is an open set and $1 \leq i' \leq I$.

Lets define

$$A \setminus W_{i'} = \bigcup_{i=1}^I W_i \setminus W_{i'}$$

taking some $i' \in I$ we have:

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i'-1} W_i \cup \bigcup_{i=i'+1}^I W_i = A'$$

Like W_i is open $\forall i \in [1, i' - 1]$ hence $\bigcup_{i=1}^{i'-1} W_i$ is open.

Like W_i is open $\forall i \in [i' + 1, I]$ hence $\bigcup_{i=i'+1}^I W_i$ is open.

Hence A' is open.

Therefore A' complement is closed.

Def. A set A in a metric space (A, d) is bounded if it has a finite generalized diameter, i.e., there is an $R < \infty$ such that $d(x, y) \leq R$ for all $x, y \in A$. A set in R^n is bounded iff it is contained inside some ball $x_1^2 + \dots + x_n^2 \leq R^2$ of finite radius R.

Proof. Like we have been defined before an open set $W_i \in A$ like an open ball such that its radius R is finite; i.e. R exists; hence A is bounded.

Therefore closed and bounded condition on Heine-Borel theorem is satisfied for A .

Hence A is compact.

Hence A manifold is compact.

[5.1] M manifold has no boundary.

Def 1. Let M be an n -dimensional manifold with boundary. Among the charts (U, ϕ) of (the maximal atlas of) M there are charts with U open in R^n (that is, disjoint from $R^{n-1} \subset R^n$). The union of images of such charts is denoted as $\text{Int } M$; it is a dense open subset of M , and it is an n -dimensional manifold in the sense of our previous definition. It is called the interior of M . The difference $M - \text{Int } M = \delta M$ is an $(n-1)$ -dimensional manifold if $\{(U, \phi)\}$ is an atlas of M , then $\{(U \cap R^{n-1}, \phi|_{U \cap R^{n-1}})\}$ is an atlas of δM . The manifold δM is called the boundary of M .

Def 2. A point $p \in M$ belongs to δM (the boundary of M) if and only if there is a chart (U, ϕ) of M such that $p = \phi(q)$ for some $q \in U \cap R^{n-1}$. (In particular, $\delta R^n = R^{n-1}$.)

Def 3. M manifold without boundary fulfilled

$$M - \text{Int } M = \delta M = \{ \} := \text{empty set}$$

[5.2 Poincares' Conjecture] If M a compact 3-dimensional manifold V without boundary is not homeomorphic to the 3-dimensional sphere then the fundamental group of V is trivial.

Proof. To be not homeomorphic establish next condition between the compact 3-dimensional manifold A without boundary and the 3-dimensional sphere:

A is non Locally Euclidean to the 3-dimensional sphere; i.e. every point $a' \in A$ has a neighbourhood which is not homeomorphic to the real 3-dimensional sphere.

Remember that in topology, the n -sphere is an example of a compact topological manifold without boundary.

This means that \exists g function such that g is bijective, continuous and inverse continuous between the open sets of both topological spaces.

Hence taking $g(a'), g(b') \in A$ a compact 3-dimensional manifold without boundary; we will have that if $g(a') = g(b')$ therefore $a' \neq b', \forall a, b \in 3$ -dimensional sphere.

Now lets take next definitions:

Def 1. The set of homotopy classes of loops in X based at "a" forms a group under the multiplication $\langle \alpha \rangle \cdot \langle \beta \rangle = \langle \alpha \cdot \beta \rangle$

Def 2. Let $f, g : X \rightarrow Y$ be maps. Then f is homotopic to g if there exists a map $F : X \times I \rightarrow Y$ such that $F(x, 0) = f(x)$ and $F(x, 1) = g(x)$ for all points $x \in X$.

Def 3. By a loop in a space X we shall understand a map $\alpha : I \rightarrow X$ such that $\alpha(0) = \alpha(1)$, \dagger and we shall say that the loop is based at the point $\alpha(0)$. If α and β are two loops based at the same point of X , we define the product $\alpha \cdot \beta$ to be the loop given by the formula:

$$\alpha \cdot \beta = \begin{cases} \alpha(2s); 0 \leq s \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \beta(2s - 1); \frac{1}{2} \leq s \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

\dagger A slight change from the terminology used when a loop was a map from a circle to X .

Def 4. The identity element is the homotopy class of the constant loop e at a defined by $e(s) = a$ for $0 \leq s \leq 1$.

By the requirement to be not homeomorphic between both topological spaces: A (compact 3-dimensional manifold without boundary) and 3-dimensional sphere; we have that f, g established on def 2 not exist.

Hence by injective property about such homeomorphism if $g(a') = g(b')$ (on the cover form by the open sets defined on early procedure to establish the image of ϕ map); $\forall g(a'), g(b') \in A$; a compact 3-dimensional manifold without boundary; only can be true if $g(s) = e(s)$ with $s \in A$.

Therefore the fundamental group of A a 3-dimensional manifold without boundary is trivial .

Remember that the loop e at "a" such that $e(s) = a$ is established $\forall a \in \mathfrak{R}$ with

$$a = \frac{l}{l'} = \frac{p \sqrt[n]{\pi^m}}{q \sqrt[n']{\pi^{m'}}}$$

i.e. is valid for every rational and irrational number on the field of \mathfrak{R} .

Conflict of Interest Statement. The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

2 References

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3 Additional References

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